

THE ROLE OF HUMAN SENSES IN CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF A HIGH INVOLVEMENT PRODUCT CATEGORY: THE CASE OF BRANDED APPAREL

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ABSTRACT

Branded apparels and related products are aspirational buys for the consumer. This exploratory study attempts to understand the role of the human senses in determining consumer buying behaviour in the specific context of apparel purchase. Empirical studies on sensory experiences are a relatively unexplored area of research in clothing and apparel buying behaviour among differently abled consumers. The senses that aid the process of product purchase such as visual, auditory and kinesthetic are the independent variables studied in this research paper. To enable a finer evaluation of buying behaviour of consumers in an apparel buying setting constructs from neuro-marketing and buyology are analysed: price, sales, promotion, advertising, impulse buying, design and trend, and are as the dependent variables studied in this research paper. The exploratory research study presents an empirical treatment of data collected from 230 respondents in the geographical area of Bengaluru. Random sampling was used as the technique for data collection while statistical tools for data analysis used KMO, communalities test, reliability, Chi square, correlation and regression analysis.

KEYWORDS

Human Senses, Impact, Selection and Buying Behaviour, Visual, Auditory, Kinaesthetic, Correlation, Regression etc.

INTRODUCTION

Apparels are aspirational products and tend to offer strong brand personalization benefits to the user. The consumers' choices depend progressively and significantly on subjective elements such as emotions, pictures, impressions and requests of the items. Apparels, as product offerings, play a role in developing a consumer's attitude while highlighting personality characteristics of a consumer. The granularity of the evoked set of factors that drive purchase decision of a consumer acquire complex dimensions when sensory variables are extended to a differently-abled consumer. The absence of a good appearance can lead to challenges associated with self-image. This can be more sensitive in the case of differently abled people. These boundaries show how the function of attire, material and building configuration groups with information of tangible issues alternate lend themselves to tactile experience.

The different dimensions that could be considered on the selection and buying behaviour of consumers considering apparel are human senses, price, design and trends, impulse buying and sales and promotion. The three senses considered here are visual, auditory and kinaesthetic senses. Since the other two senses which are taste and smell, do not play a role in the selection of apparel and does not affect the buying behaviour of consumers are not considered in this study.

Visual senses play a key role in affect the self-image of the consumer and actions that trigger arousal to buy apparel. It also depends on how the individual looks at the apparel and how the apparel appears to the eye of the individual. The eye level could be affected by how the clothes are displayed, the mannequins display, the design and many others factors. The visual effects could be in 2D or 3D effects. The display could be through a picture or in real, which relates to other human senses that could help in apparel selection. The visual reactions can excite neural impulses, which could impact on neuro framework on the individual and facilitate appropriate decision making. Auditory sense, stirs a considerable measure of emotions amid the determination and the path toward purchasing an

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apparel product. Tuning into individuals about most recent patterns and form, impact people in determination and purchasing of apparels and texture. Auditory factors, as similar to word of mouth, in shopping play a major role in the selection of apparel. Kinaesthetic sense allows for the selection of apparel as also the feeling of the fabric and the texture.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Dash, Mihir; Akshaya (2014) explores visual impact on apparel purchase and examines the role of store layout, mannequin display, promotional advertisement, product display and so on in understanding the buying behaviour of consumers.

Wu, Juanjuan; WonJu, Hae; Kim, Jieun; Damminga, Cara; Kim, HyeYoung (2012) e. investigates the role of colour, visual texture and style effect factors in the purchase of products as also the interest of consumers, pleasure perception and purchase behaviour. This exploratory study explored the impact of style, colour and visual appeal among consumers accessing virtual stores.

Wang, Ying; Chen, Yan; Zhi-ge, Chen (2006) explores consumers' perception (sensory engineering) influence on the senses, feelings and design perception. The study concluded that the senses could be related to the purchase behaviour of clothing.

Osmud Rahman (2003) depicts how visual and file input have an effect on purchase intention of denim apparel. Both sensory and cognitive responses were investigated using quantitative methods. The conclusions drawn from the research indicated that the respondents were specific to the fabric feel, fitting, physical durability and the visual aspects of the product in denim purchase evaluation.

Subhani, Muhammad Imtiaz; Hasan, Syed Akif; Osman, Amber (2011) study how apparels have an impact on the mood of consumers. The effect could be based on the feel, personality and other demographic factors. The paper also depicts how the mood of the individual has an effect on the dressing behaviour of the individual. There could be a number of other factors that could affect the dressing behaviour of an individual. The factors such as emotions, quality of the fabric, situations, print, design, colour, education of a person etc., could be useful in identifying an individual.

Song, Kun; Fiore, Ann Marie; Park, Jihye (2006) explored how the online shopping experience influenced consumers in the selection and buying behaviour of apparel. The online experience helps in bringing about a different perception as virtual shopping experience is not taken into account and this could be a negative aspect about online shopping. Telepresence experience and the fantasy could influence shopping experience.

Methods: A dress displayed at a retail establishment or a promotion may draw thought, and also energize diverse classy responses. Regardless, if the watcher hates the presence of a dress, he or she may not wish to take a glance at the thing further, for instance, by feeling the texture or endeavouring the piece of attire on. Along these lines, it is obvious that just by advertisements or other such means the customer needs can't be fulfilled. Hence, there is a need to focus the impact on how the human senses influence the determination of attire. The empirical study is specific to the geographical region of Bangalore. This particular study depicts how the conceptual factors like senses and the selection affect the buying behaviour of customers considering recent researches regarding similar concepts the study is further looked at in a detailed manner.

OBJECTIVES

- To measure the impact of sensory on demographic variables.
- To understand the impact of sensory on a selection of apparel.
- To analyse the impact of senses on buying behaviour of apparel.

HYPOTHESES

- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on demographic factors.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on age.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on gender.
- There is no significant relationship between the senses and their impact on qualification.

There is no significant relationship between senses (visual, auditory and kinaesthetic) and selection behaviour of the consumer.

There is no significant relationship between the sensory appeals and buying behaviour of the consumer.

Sampling Plan: The data population included apparel consumers in engaged in browser mode shopping in speciality store format setting. The respondent data was collected using a structured questionnaire perceptions .The judgmental sampling method with inclusion parameters (age, location, gender and so on) was applied to the sample population.

Sample Size: Respondent data from 230 samples were collected belonging to varied demographics.

Sample Frame: the sample of respondents were drawn from the geographical area of Bangalore i.e., East, West, North, South and Central Zones, which included mall intercepts as a contact method.

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Tools: The software used was SPSS Software and the tools used were: frequency distribution; Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin to test the sampling adequacy; Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity; Communality test to determine the correlation among the variables in a dataset; reliability to check the extent to which assessments are consistent; Chi-Square Test; correlation; and regression.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analyses is broadly classified into three approaches, namely:

- Frequency and descriptive statistics
- Test of the adequacy of the sample (KMO) and reliability tools
- Decision tools such as Chi-square, correlation, and regression.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Test Adequacy of Sample

Table-1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.788
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4044.520
	d.f.	1225
	Sig.	.000

Sources: Authors Compilation

Normally, $0 < KMO < 1$

If $KMO > 0.5$, the sample is adequate.

Here, $KMO = 0.788$ which indicates that the sample is adequate and we may proceed with the Factor Analysis.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Taking a 95% level of Significance, $\alpha=0.05$

The p-value (Sig.) of $000 < 0.05$, therefore the Factor Analysis is valid.

As $p < \alpha$, therefore the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) is accepted indicating that there may be a statistically significant interrelationship between variables.

The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test measure of sampling adequacy was used to examine the appropriateness of Factor Analysis. The approximate of Chi-Square is 4044.520 with 1225 degrees of freedom, which is significant at 0.05 Level of Significance. The KMO statistic of 0.788 is also large (greater than 0.50). Hence, Factor Analysis is considered as an appropriate technique for further Analysis of the data.

B. Reliability Statistics

Table-2: Reliability for the Different Dimensions

Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
1. Visual	.703	8
2. Auditory	.70	6
3. Kinaesthetic	.683	7
4. Design & Trend	.778	7
5. Price	.693	6
6. Impulse Buying	.683	6
7. Sales / Promotion / Advertisement	.693	6
8. Buying Behaviour	.725	4

Sources: Authors Compilation

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than 0.6 and some are more than 0.7 which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent responses to the items of the concerned constructs. An average of 0.707 is computed for a total of 50 items.

C. Chi-Square Analysis

1. Hypothesis Testing For Visual Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of customers.

Table-3: Chi-Square Tests: Visual Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Customers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	257.428 ^a	220	.042
Likelihood Ratio	172.239	220	.993
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.938	1	.005
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (257.428, $p=0.042$) is less than the table value (0.05) the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant relationship between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between visual sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

2. Hypothesis Testing For Auditory Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the Buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-4: Chi-Square Tests: Auditory Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	157.868 ^a	140	.143
Likelihood Ratio	126.324	140	.790
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.513	1	.004
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (157.868, p=0.143) is more than the table value (0.05), the alternate hypothesis is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is no inference between auditory sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

3. Hypothesis Testing For Kinaesthetic Sensory Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is a significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-5: Chi-Square Tests: Kinaesthetic Sensory Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	184.376 ^a	150	.029
Likelihood Ratio	154.902	150	.375
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.285	1	.131
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

Result: Since the Pearson Chi-Square calculated value (184.376, p=0.029) is less than the table value (0.05) so the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. There is significant relationship between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Inference: Thus there is an inference between kinaesthetic sensory factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

4. Hypothesis Testing for Design and Trend Factors versus Buying Behaviour of Consumers

H₀: There is no significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.
 H₁: There is a significant relationship between design and trend factors and the buying behaviour of consumers.

Table-6: Chi-Square Tests: Design and Trend Factors and the Buying Behaviour of Consumers

	Value	d.f.	Asymp. Sig. (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	190.587 ^a	180	.280
Likelihood Ratio	158.756	180	.871
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.967	1	.026
N of Valid Cases	89		

Sources: Authors Compilation

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